

THAILAND “ASIA AND AFRICA PROGRAMME” STAKEHOLDER ENGAGEMENT STRATEGY 2020 - 2025

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The Thailand Asia and Africa Programme (AAP), otherwise known as the Mahidol Oxford Tropical Medicine Research Unit (MORU), was established in 1979 as a research collaboration between Mahidol University (Thailand) and the University of Oxford (UK), and core-funded by the UK’s Wellcome Trust. Our main office and laboratories are located within the Faculty of Tropical Medicine at Mahidol University in Bangkok, Thailand, with hubs and study sites across Thailand, Asia and Africa.

The Thailand AAP exists to improve the health of people in the resource-poor tropics. Our core activity is clinical research, including multi-site clinical trials on tropical diseases such as malaria, melioidosis, scrub typhus, and on maternal and child health. We also conduct laboratory studies, epidemiology studies, mathematical modelling, social and ethics research. Our research is often conducted alongside provision of healthcare, sometimes in partnership with local non government organisations (NGOs) (e.g. Medical Action Myanmar, Angkor Hospital for Children). We are unique among global health research institutions in that we have a separate department —the Department of Bioethics and Engagement — dedicated to bioethics and engagement and their intersection.

A. Vision and scope

Our vision is to embed meaningful engagement at the core of all Thailand AAP programmes, in addition to the procedures that are already in place to support ethical research. We will provide guidance, training and support to AAP students and researchers to help them: within each programme, identify relevant stakeholders to engage with; develop aims and an appropriate plan of engagement activities; and evaluate whether the engagement outcomes have been achieved.

Thailand AAP programmes often involve large and complex partnerships, with a wide range of individuals and organizations that work within, or collaborate with, the programme in various ways. There are three types of programmes in the Thailand AAP:

Type 1	A specific research study e.g. triple combination antimalarial vs dual combination antimalarial study in Africa and Asia
Type 2	A series of studies planned sequentially or a group of complementary studies (e.g. Malaria Infection Studies in Thailand)
Type 3	A long-standing health programme (e.g. >30 year antenatal care programme on the Thai-Myanmar border, tuberculosis programme on the Thai-Myanmar border).

B. Stakeholders

A stakeholder of a programme is an individual or organization that holds a legitimate, non-trivial, interest in the conduct and/or outcomes of the programme. Each programme creates a unique collection of individuals and organizations whose interests may be affected by the programme.(1)

This creates four categories of stakeholders for us.

1. Programme Participants

These are individual participants in our programme. For Type 1 and 2 programmes, they are research participants of clinical trials and other studies. For Type 3 programmes, they are individuals directly involved in health programmes, such as the pregnant women who attend our antenatal care clinics, and tuberculosis patients, who are part of our TB programme on the Thai-Myanmar border.

2. Programme-affiliated stakeholders

Programme-affiliated stakeholders are individuals or organizations/institutions who have roles or functions within the programme (e.g., co-investigators, staff, partner organizations) or enable it (e.g., funders, investors, industry partners), or contribute to its execution/operations (e.g., implementation partners, collaborators). In some programmes, policy makers may be considered programme-affiliated stakeholders e.g. in most malaria related studies, the National Malaria Control Programmes are our collaborators.

3. External stakeholders

External stakeholders are often referred to generically as “the community”, but the category is usually broader than the geographically-bounded, pre-existing associations that the term implies e.g. families of patients enrolled in our TB programme.

They might be patient or disease groups, communities of interest, or demographic groups (e.g. teenagers, school children, mothers, teachers, scientific community).

4. General public

The “general public”, who are external stakeholders by definition, but whose interests may be remote from the conduct and outcomes of the research.

The ‘public’ includes individuals and groups who do not currently have a formal relationship with a higher education institution through teaching, research or knowledge transfer. (2)

C. Outcomes

Our engagement work has three interrelated outcomes and supports the AAP’s overall mission to improve the health and wellbeing of people in the resource-poor tropics. (See Appendix 1. Thailand AAP Stakeholder Engagement Theory of Change Framework)

Outcome 1: MORU programmes are *trustworthy*

“Trustworthy” means that our programmes are “able to be relied on as honest or truthful” by our stakeholders (Oxford English Dictionary).

Aims

To achieve this outcome, our aim is to **build relationships** with our stakeholders in deliberate and meaningful ways. (3)

In our relationship building activities we will pay attention to:

- the social, cultural and economic contexts of our stakeholders, in particular to disadvantaged and/or vulnerable groups
- diversity and inclusion in our engagement activities including hard-to-reach groups (4)
- accessibility of our engagement activities
- opinions and lived experiences of our stakeholders
- responsiveness and reciprocity in our exchanges

Outcome 2: The potential health *impacts* of MORU programmes are maximised

Through our engagement activities we seek to maximize the potential health impact of our programmes. This means that health problems of national, regional or global importance are improved through changes in policy and/or practice and policy (where applicable).

Aims

To achieve this outcome, our aims are:

(a) To **share** our research and knowledge with our stakeholders

This means that we communicate and discuss our programmes (including objectives, procedures and findings) to relevant stakeholders. We tailor this communication according to each stakeholder group and each programme type. Where applicable, the public is able to use data and evidence generated by our research (e.g. improve their understanding, appreciate science, behavior change).

(b) To **listen and learn** from our stakeholders and embed the learning into our programmes

This maximises our ability to respond to public concerns and interest and more likely to achieve their intended scientific aims, and thereby their impact is maximized.

Outcome 3: MORU programmes are ethical

Our programmes are ethical because they consider other people's **interests**.

This means that:

- 1) we recognize and respect our stakeholders and their interests
- 2) we determine appropriate benefits in consultation with programme participants and programme-affiliated stakeholders
- 3) we minimize risks and burdens for our stakeholders (e.g. third party risks for human infection studies, family members for TB patients)
- 4) we have a good consent process for our programme participants
- 5) we understand the vulnerabilities of our programme participants
- 6) we gain appropriate permissions and approvals (beyond formal approvals e.g. from relevant ethics committees)

Aims

To achieve this outcome, we aim to:

(a) **Identify** the different groups of programme stakeholders, their interests —especially non-obvious ones—that might be affected by any specific programme (i.e., the potential for harm) and to determine what responses these interests might create for us.

- Who are the programme-affiliated and external stakeholders?
- What are their interests (including economic, reputational, safety etc)?
- Response – to what extent do we need to change the programme design, procedures, location, timing? What other engagement activities are needed as a response?

(b) To **listen and learn** from our stakeholders and embed the learning into our programmes

This maximises the benefits and impact, and minimizes any potential harms of our programmes.

D. Key Activities

We have grouped our activities into six types. A SWOT analysis of all activities can be found at the end of this section (Table 1).

1. Advisory groups

Why?

We currently have two advisory groups i.e. the Tak Province Community Ethics Advisory Board (T-CAB) in Mae Sot,(5, 6) and the Young Persons Advisory Group (YPAG) in Siem Reap,(7) two locations where we have established community-based work.

Tak Province Border Community Ethics Advisory Board, or T-CAB, was formed on the Thai-Myanmar border in 2009. It serves multiple programmes run by the Shoklo Malaria Research Unit, which operates on the Thai-Myanmar border. The T-CAB is involved in broad portfolio of programmes; they are trusted by us to provide feedback and influence our programmes. Currently, the T-CAB has 13 members, and they meet with our researchers every 4 to 6 weeks.

The YPAG was formed in 2015, comprised of 10 to 15 year-old children living around the Cambodia Oxford Medical Research Unit catchment area. The YPAG currently has 35 members and meets our researchers/collaborators every 4-6 weeks.

Through frequent meetings with our advisory groups, we have been able to build strong relationships with their members and the community they come from (external stakeholders). The formal meetings and informal conversations in between meetings provide a platform for honest feedback. These strong relationships and open discussions increase the trustworthiness of our programmes. (Outcome 1)

Advisory groups also help us improve the impact of our programmes in a variety of ways. For example, the YPAG members co-created an AMR-themed play with researchers in 2018. The play was performed by YPAG members to staff and patients at the Angkor Hospital for Children hospital (our NGO partner) in conjunction with AMR day to raise awareness about AMR.

Secondly, we obtain feedback on practical and design aspects of our programme e.g. T-CAB members have advised us on how to improve the number of pregnant women who use our antenatal services at SMRU. This illustrates that advisory groups help our programmes to be more accessible and acceptable to the communities we serve, thereby increasing its impact. (Outcome 2)

Thirdly, our research results are often shared with advisory group members and they in turn disseminate the information back to the community (e.g. around 300,000 people in the T-CAB catchment area) so that the community can then use this information as they see fit.

In addition, advisory group members also advise us on how to engage the wider public or help us refine our engagement strategies targeted to the general public.

Advisory groups also improve the ethics of our programmes (Outcome 3), for example members provide advice on operational aspects of studies (e.g. frequency of visits), determine how much compensation to provide, and help us review participant information sheets.

Our plans

We are planning to have three advisory groups instead of two. We plan to continue developing the T-CAB and YPAG. In addition, we are currently piloting an advisory group in Bangkok (Health Research Ethics Interest Group or HREIG).

Unlike the T-CAB or the YPAG, the HREIG is not linked to a specific community. They comprise of members who live in the Bangkok metropolitan area, independent of the AAP, our partners or our participants. They represent voices of the “public” and as such, this will enable us to seek unbiased “public” voices on specific aspects of research and advice on how to engage the wider public.

2. Participatory and science-arts collaborations

Why?

In the last core grant period (2015-2019), we have successfully conducted several projects under this category.

They are “Village Drama Against Malaria” (VDAM) (2016-2019 (8, 9), “Under the Mask” film on tuberculosis (2019; see Box 1), “Fishy Clouds”, an AMR play (2016, 2018) (10), and “Fever and Antibiotics” (2019) forum theatre. They address some of our most important research areas such as malaria elimination, TB and AMR.

The projects that fall in this category have several things in common. Firstly, they are developed and delivered in partnership with “programme-affiliated stakeholders”. For example, the partners in the VDAM project are village leaders, village malaria workers, local drama groups and school teachers. These partnerships ensure that our engagement strategy is culturally appropriate, responsive to the community, and we understand how communities prefer to be engaged. For example, we chose drama as a means of communication about malaria based on advice by our local Cambodian partners. In addition, the relationships cultivated during the preparation and delivery of the project build trust and mutual understanding with our local partners (Outcome 1).

Secondly, these projects are designed to maximize listening and learning from the community. For example, in our TB film project on the Thai-Myanmar, we gathered stories from TB patients and their families prior to writing the script. Their stories help our researchers listen and learn about challenges faced by TB patients, their families, friends and neighbours. We have embedded our learning to improve our screening, counselling and treatment strategies, which in turn improves the ethics (Outcome 3) and impact (Outcome 2) of our TB programme. We have also identified the relevant interests of patients’ families (external stakeholders) that might be affected by our programmes – families potentially have to cope with the economic loss if the breadwinner of the family is undergoing longterm treatment at our clinic.

Thirdly, the end product of these projects (e.g. drama performance, TB film) reach large audiences who are often illiterate and live in rural communities. For example, the TB film, which was made in Burmese, has been shown in 16 villages, 35 migrant schools and to more than 10,800 audience members on the Thai-Myanmar border (figures at 11 Oct 2019). After every screening, there is a discussion session with the TB clinic team. After watching the film, many villagers have come to get screened for TB. This increases the impact of our TB programme to improve the health of the population along the border (Outcome 2).

Finally, creative partners such as filmmakers and drama performers bring a different lens to our research. They also have a different training and skillsets when approaching engagement, which means that materials co-created with them will likely to be more accessible and usable by the public.

Our plans

We plan to continue the VDAM project but will increase active participation from children and young people in the performance. As for the TB film, we will continue screening the film in Burmese rural villages. We will also dub the film in Karen and screen them in Karen villages.

3. Festivals and themed events

Why?

The Thailand AAP has contributed to festivals and themed events like “Antibiotic Awareness Week” (Fishy Clouds, an AMR puppet theatre), “World Malaria Day” (VDAM) and “World TB Day” (premiere screening of “Under the Mask” in March 2019). These events, usually run at a large scale, are aimed at the general public, led by government departments and bring together multiple partners to gain ‘critical mass’, which can help reach larger audiences. These events usually involve thousand visitors per day. The activities vary depending on the theme and the most effective method of engagement of each location. They usually incorporate an exhibition to share our knowledge (e.g. on AMR) or an interactive element to create an opportunity for us to learn from the e.g. short questionnaires, games (Outcome 2).

In addition, our presence and contribution serves to raise public awareness about the role of the AAP in locally relevant health research.

Participating in national and international awareness campaigns also helps us to strengthen our existing partnerships (to increase trust – Outcome 1) with the government, charities and cultural organisations, and to create new collaborations.

Our Plans

We will aim to participate 2-3 such events a year, including new events e.g. 'IF Oxford' Festival of Science and Ideas (<https://if-oxford.com/about/>), or the Bangkok Red Cross Fair. We will prioritise events that focus on our priority areas (e.g. malaria, AMR) and the needs of harder-to-reach audiences, for example by running events in locations that our audiences attend as part of their daily lives (e.g. villages square or malls). (4)

4. Public talks

Why?

We have organized science café and “Pint of Science” (PoS) events in Laos, Cambodia and Thailand since 2016. (11, 12) We started the first science café in Laos and Cambodia. Due to the political system and history there are few opportunities for open debate on topics of science and technology in Laos and Cambodia. Launching these two science cafés has been an engagement milestone for us.

The Pint of Science festival (<https://www.pintofscienceth.com/>) is the biggest annual international science festival usually held over three days in May each year. In May 2017, led by a senior microbiologist, we coordinated the first Pint of Science festival in Asia. (11, 13)

The Pint of Science and science cafés events are typically held in traditionally non-academic venues such as cafes and pubs, to attract the public (40-80 attendees per event) who do not usually attend academic talks. These events provide opportunities for many researchers of all levels to be involved in PE. As of October 2019 we have facilitated 60 PoS talks to nearly 700 people in Thailand. Unlike PoS events in other countries which charge a small fee, our events are free to ensure that we are inclusive, i.e. we do not exclude students from poorer backgrounds. Through these events researchers share their research, methods, challenges and joys of research with the public, so that the public can use the knowledge as they see fit (Outcome 2).

Through participation in these events, researchers improve their communication skills and creativity in their delivery. On most event days, we also invite researchers from other universities and institutions to give talks. This potentially creates new opportunities for partnerships, and spreads the engagement culture where we work. We have noted that having talks from a different field (e.g. decoding cave paintings, drones) attracts a different segment of the public.

Our Plans

We plan to continue these events and organize special events for young people and school children.

5. Stakeholder engagement workshops

Why?

Stakeholder engagement workshops (StEWs) focus on strategic and planning aspects of our engagement activities. Participants are drawn from all of stakeholder groups, as well as AAP researchers and engagement staff. Outputs of these workshops are for example stakeholder maps for new projects, a list of aims and objectives for engagement with different stakeholder groups, and ideas for engagement activities. This ensures that our work responds to stakeholder concerns and interests. These workshops also help us identify any ethical issues that our programmes might create (Outcome 3).

Stakeholder workshops also strengthen our relationships with existing and new partners and helps us to achieve Outcome 1.

In addition, StEWs are an important part of our evaluation strategy, for example to gain feedback on our engagement activities and to share what we have learnt. For example, two VDAM Theory of Change Workshops were conducted in Cambodia 2019 as part of our evaluation initiative.

Our Plans

We plan to hold regular StEWs linked to our bigger engagement projects (e.g. VDAM, Under the Mask). We will also pilot them in context of research programmes, to inform engagement activities and, potentially, research directions.

6. Engagement Bursaries

Why?

In 2018, we launched Thailand AAP Public Engagement Bursaries. The bursary scheme funds small projects, new engagement ideas and seed projects, as well as aims to support less experienced researchers in leading their own projects. Projects qualify for funding if they address one of our 3 engagement outcomes or capacity building in engagement.

Our bursary projects enable researchers from all career stages to lead their own engagement activities. Within each bursary project team, a total of 3-10 other researchers and students are involved in the planning and implementation. These projects enable many researchers and students to be involved in engagement. They have also generated many new ideas and expand our network and partnerships. Researchers can use it to pilot an idea prior to organizing a larger project.

Our plans

We plan to continue the bursary programme, but will scale down the number of awarded bursaries to 2-3 per year.

7. Dialogue, small group meetings, consultations etc

Why?

Dialogue, meetings and consultations with community leaders, potential programme participants and their communities are held throughout the life cycle of a programme i.e. from inception to the end of the project. The shape, format, and frequency is highly dependent on the type of programme, location and context. For example in our mass antimalarial drug administration studies in Cambodia, Laos and Myanmar, an extensive community engagement initiative was embedded in the programme. This included house-to-house visits, village meetings, and consultation with local leaders. (14-17)

These meetings are essential to ensure that our programmes address priority areas so that they are more impactful (Outcome 2), and complement instead of undermine existing local initiatives and are ethically acceptable to the community (Outcome 3). Ideally these conversations also result in collaborative partnerships with key stakeholders. (Outcome 1)

Our plans

We plan to continue including these types of small-scale, 'deep engagement' meetings in our programmes and projects.

Table 1. SWOT analysis of our activity types

Activity	Strengths/Opportunities	Weaknesses/Threats
Advisory groups	Build strong, trusting relationships, deep level of engagement	Only a small part of the community can be members, resource-intensive
Participatory and science-arts collaborations	Build strong, trusting relationships, moderate level of engagement, potential to lead to positive behavior change, large audiences	Resource-intensive, expensive, need big teams (researchers, engagement team, creative partners)
Festivals and themed events	Large audiences, more likely to attract hard-to-reach audiences, synergy with other partners	Short interactions, science festival culture less established in Asia
Public talks	Cheap, can involve many researchers from all career stages, moderate sized audiences (40-80 attendees per talk)	Short interactions, resource-intensive, might not attract hard-to-reach audiences
Stakeholder workshops	Generates new engagement ideas and audiences, builds new relationships and strengthens existing ones, mix of audience groups by design	Resource-intensive, group set-up needs to be designed carefully to avoid 'echo chamber' effect

Engagement bursaries	Many researchers can lead and be trained on engagement, many ideas generated, and networks expanded, researchers can promote culture change	High administrative burden, highly dependent on individuals
Dialogue, small group meetings, consultations etc	Essential for the success of any programme, can initiate collaborative partnerships	Risk of disappointment if priority areas are pre-determined e.g. set by funders

E. Supportive structures

1. Commitment and leadership

The Thailand AAP has a dedicated department, the Department of Bioethics and Engagement, which is responsible for leading the implementation of the new Thailand AAP Stakeholder Engagement Strategy. It provides oversight and coordinates all engagement activities and engagement capacity building within the network. The head of the Department also serves as the academic lead for engagement. She is a member of the Science & Strategy Committee, the highest level committee at the AAP. This ensures that engagement is integrated into the AAP workflow, day-to-day management practices, and reporting and accountability structures.

2. Skilled engagement staff

We have core engagement teams in Bangkok, Oxford and other major research sites (e.g. Mae Sot, Siem Reap, Pailin, Vientiane) equivalent to 10 “full time equivalents”. The core team members are experienced and skilled, and lead engagement projects at their respective sites (e.g. Village Drama Against Malaria project, Young Persons’ Advisory Group) as well as support researcher-led engagement activities, e.g. Pint of Science events. They also serve as engagement “champions” at the AAP, at our research sites and with our partners, and provide support for bursary projects.

In addition to the core team, each large programme has their own engagement team such as the engagement team related to our recent mass antimalarial drug administration study.

3. Engagement capacity and training

We have ongoing training for engagement staff and researchers who conduct or plan to conduct engagement activities. This includes organizing specific skills training workshops, sharing of online training resources, mentorship via public engagement bursary awards, inductions for new staff and students, and regional meetings (e.g. those co-organised with the Vietnam AAP).

4. Evidence, excellence and scholarship on engagement

In addition to delivering engagement projects, we conduct engagement research that contributes to the growing evidence base for engagement in global health programs. The evidence generated may offer important new insights to help us improve our own work and

those of others. We will continue to create an environment to strive for good quality engagement work.

5. Societal and cultural partnerships enable staff to engage with the public

Our engagement work has involved:

(1) local governments partners e.g. AMR dictionary project – Ministry of Public Health Thailand, in the Village Drama Against Malaria project - National Malaria Control Programme staff, village malaria workers, school teachers

(2) non-governmental organisations e.g. Southeast Asia Junction, Mae Tao Clinic for “In our Voices” photo exhibition (<http://seajunction.org/event/panel-discussion-and-opening-exhibition-in-our-voices-health-resilience-along-the-thailand-myanmar-border/>)

(3) Creative partners e.g. FilmAid Foundation, a non-profit humanitarian organization, based in Mae Sot (for the TB film), “Arts for All”, a forum theatre company based in Yangon (Fever and antibiotics forum theatre), B-Floor theatre (“Fishy Clouds”, a puppet theatre on antimicrobial resistance)

We will continue to strengthen existing relationships and work with new partners for our engagement work. For example, in the next phase of screening the TB film, we will partner with International Organisation for Migration and World Vision. These new partners will enable us to reach different audiences and have access to different locations.

Our evaluation work results showed that local leadership - not merely partnership - improves the reach and effectiveness of a project. Hence we plan to involve local partners as early as possible and as much as possible in the AAP work, as well as the related engagement efforts. We also plan to develop more partnerships via engagement activities such as our stakeholder engagement workshops.

In addition, we will continue to work with engagement teams in other Wellcome-funded programmes, at the University of Oxford (Vietnam AAP, Kenya AAP), through the UK’s National Coordinating Centre for Public Engagement (NCCPE) (<https://www.publicengagement.ac.uk/>) and the online MESH Community Engagement Network (<https://mesh.tghn.org/>).

F. The changes we hope to achieve and related indicators

The Bioethics & Engagement department was established in April 2015. Prior to this there were very few engagement activities that address outcomes 1 and 2. Now we have a team, strategy and a diverse range of activities. In the next five years, we would like to see the following changes:

Table 2. Changes we want to see and example indicators

Changes	Example Indicators (non-exhaustive)
Increase in the number and diversity of researchers leading or taking part	Total number and percentage of researchers involved in engagement (and by gender, career stages and research disciplines);

in engagement activities	membership in national or international guidelines committees; numbers and percentage of researcher-led activities
Overall increase number and diversity of stakeholders (including public) engaged	Number of audience/participants including those “hard-to-reach” participated in engagement activities e.g. Pint of Science events; participatory theatre
Increase in the number of programmes that has engagement activities that address outcomes 1 and 2	Number of researchers that consult advisory boards or that have their own engagement activities
Increase in researchers’ capacity to conduct engagement	Number approved vs rejected bursary applications (due to quality), resources needed by core engagement team to help researcher-led engagement plans, number of engagement trainings offered and number of attendees
Increase in the extent of involvement and leadership of local partners in engagement activities	Extent of involvement and leadership of local partners in the planning, implementation and evaluation of engagement activities
Increase the number and quality of evaluation activities	Number of evaluation reports and academic papers on engagement (and number of citations)

G. Monitoring and Evaluation Plans

Each engagement initiative related to a specific programme will have its own unique collection of stakeholders, outcomes, and related indicators. Below is a list of potential evaluation questions and indicators for a given activity.

The evaluation plans are targeted towards outcomes 1, 2 and 3 and complements section F.

Table 3. Evaluation questions and example indicators

Evaluation questions for Outcome 1 - MORU programmes are trustworthy	Example indicators (non-exhaustive)
What is the nature of the relationships between MORU and its stakeholders?	Positive attitudes of stakeholders towards MORU researchers, extent of diversity of partnerships
What attitudes do our different stakeholder groups, in particular external ones, have of the programme and our engagement work?	Positive attitudes of stakeholders towards MORU programmes and engagement work
What is the nature of feedback from	Constructive, honest and critical feedback

stakeholders?	from advisory groups e.g. what type of questions/concerns did we glean from stakeholders?
To what extent are stakeholders' opinions acknowledged or acted upon?	Changes in the programme design, objectives or procedures where applicable; explanations and negotiations if changes cannot be made e.g. due to budget constraints
Evaluation questions for Outcome 2 - The potential <i>impacts</i> of MORU programmes are maximized.	Example indicators (non-exhaustive)
What are the changes in practice and policy advanced by engagement work (if relevant)?	Changes in practice and policy attributable to engagement
How much research and knowledge did we share with our stakeholders?	Number of public talks and workshops to discuss research findings; number of presentations of findings to advisory groups
How much did they take away?	Stakeholders desire for behaviour change; have improved understanding of subject matter
What did we learn from our stakeholders that we did not already know?	Learning about stakeholders concerns that we did not know before and how we responded to them
How did we embed this learning into our programmes?	Changes in the programme design, objectives or procedures as a result of learning
How did we build on our learning from previous activities when designing an engagement strategy?	Changes in the engagement design, venue, activity type where applicable
Evaluation questions for Outcome 3 – Our programmes are <i>ethical</i>	Example indicators (non-exhaustive)
To what extent did we recognize and respect our stakeholders and their interests?	Ethical issues and relevant interest identified through engagement activities that we were not aware of
To what extent did our programmes provide appropriate benefits and minimised harms to programme participants?	Health impact to the programme community, other indirect benefits, steps taken to minimise harms
Did we gain appropriate formal and informal permissions?	Time taken to obtain approvals, any complaints from gatekeepers

Are our consent processes appropriate?	Quality of participant information sheets and consent processes
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